

SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH OF THE SCO COUNTRIES: SYNERGY AND INTEGRATION

上合组织国家的科学研究：协同和一体化

**Proceedings of the
International Conference**

**Date:
April 10**

Beijing, China 2024

上合组织国家的科学研究：协同和一体化
国际会议

参与者的英文报告

**International Conference
“Scientific research of the SCO
countries: synergy and integration”**

Part 2

2024 年 4 月 10 日。中国北京
April 10, 2024. Beijing, PRC

Proceedings of the International Conference
**“Scientific research of the SCO countries: synergy
and integration”** - Reports in English

(April 10, 2024. Beijing, PRC)

ISBN 978-5-905695-82-7

这些会议文集结合了会议的材料 – 学术论文和科学工作者的论文报告。它考察了职业化人格的技术和社会学问题。一些文章涉及人格职业化研究问题的理论和方法论方法和原则。

作者对所引用的出版物，事实，数字，引用，统计数据，专有名称和其他信息的准确性负责

These Conference Proceedings combine materials of the conference – research papers and thesis reports of scientific workers. They examine technical, juridical and sociological aspects of research issues. Some articles deal with theoretical and methodological approaches and principles of research questions of personality professionalization.

Authors are responsible for the accuracy of cited publications, facts, figures, quotations, statistics, proper names and other information.

ISBN 978-5-905695-82-7

©Scientific publishing house Infinity, 2024

©Group of authors, 2024

CONTENTS

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

大电流雷电放电数值模拟

Basic provisions of the concept of the economic model the functioning of the free port of Vladivostok

Fisenko Andrey Ivanovich.....9

“人力资本”、“劳动潜力”、“人力潜力”概念的比率

The ratio of the concepts of "human capital", "labor potential", "human potential"

Cherkesova Elvira Yurievna, Turbanov Vladimir Victorovich.....14

制裁限制下企业的竞争力：现代特征和结构组成

Competitiveness of enterprises under sanctions restrictions: modern features and structural components

Larin Sergey Nikolaevich, Khrustalev Oleg Evgenievich.....19

企业智力潜力的概念：定义、经济本质与结构

The concept of intellectual potential of an enterprise: definition, economic essence and structure

Larin Sergey Nikolaevich, Khrustalev Evgeniy Yurievich26

中小企业作为公共部门的受益者

Small and medium-sized businesses as beneficiaries of the public sector

Loshinskaya Elena Nikolaevna.....33

白俄罗斯共和国自然和技术紧急情况经济损失评估概念框架

Conceptual framework for assessing economic damage from natural and technogenic emergencies in the Republic of Belarus

Lopatchouk Olga Nikolaevna39

SDG-6：俄罗斯确保所有人获得水和卫生设施并进行可持续管理的关键技术领域有哪些

SDG-6: What are crucial technological areas for Russia to ensure availability and sustainable management of water and sanitation for all

Epstein Alexander Dmitrievich, Shkaredo Victoria Alexandrovna,

Li Arina Alexandrovna.....45

俄罗斯联邦高等教育“大学竞争力”类别的含义和方面

The meaning and aspects of the category “University competitiveness” for higher education in Russian Federation

Sorokin Mikhail.....51

制裁限制下企业的竞争力：现代特征和结构组成
**COMPETITIVENESS OF ENTERPRISES UNDER SANCTIONS
RESTRICTIONS: MODERN FEATURES AND STRUCTURAL
COMPONENTS**

Larin Sergey Nikolaevich

Candidate of Technical Sciences, Leading Researcher

Khrustalev Oleg Evgenievich

Candidate of Economic Sciences, Senior Researcher

*Central Economics and Mathematics Institute of the Russian Academy
of Sciences, Moscow, Russia*

注解。 制裁限制对国内企业的竞争产生了负面影响，使其处于明显不利的境地。 因此，对于俄罗斯企业在国际市场上的竞争行为，竞争力的概念已经获得了新的经济本质。 本研究的主要目的是阐明竞争力概念的经济本质及其与俄罗斯经济发展现代现实相关的组成部分。 为了实现这一目标，该研究采用了经济信息综合和分析的方法。 研究结果明确了企业竞争力的概念及其与制裁限制条件相关的结构组成部分。

关键词：俄罗斯经济、制裁限制、企业竞争力。

Annotation. *The sanctions restrictions had a negative impact on the competition of domestic enterprises, as they put them in obviously unfavorable conditions. Therefore, the concept of competitiveness has acquired a new economic essence in relation to the conduct of competition by Russian enterprises in international markets. The main goal of this study is to clarify the economic essence of the concept of competitiveness, as well as its components in relation to the modern realities of the development of the Russian economy. To achieve this goal, the study used methods of synthesis and analysis of economic information. As a result of the study, the concept of competitiveness of enterprises and its structural components in relation to the conditions of sanctions restrictions were clarified.*

Keywords: *Russian economy, sanctions restrictions, enterprise competitiveness.*

Introduction.

For many Russian enterprises, sanctions restrictions have become an additional factor in the negative impact of the external environment on the development of their production sector. Countries, economic sectors and individual enterprises

that are faced with the impact of sanctions restrictions are forced to make additional efforts to maintain their competitiveness, primarily in international markets. Over the past twenty years, the practice of applying sanctions restrictions in economic relations has expanded significantly. Considering that sanctions restrictions usually mean a number of long- or short-term measures aimed at creating unfavorable conditions for the normal development of the country's economy as a whole, its individual industries and enterprises [1], there is a need to determine their effectiveness, on the one hand, and on the other hand, the possibility of adapting individual countries, economic sectors and enterprises to various kinds of restrictions. These circumstances lead to an intensification of competition, as a result of which only the most efficient manufacturers, whose products fully meet the needs and expectations of potential consumers, will remain in the markets. This article will substantiate the feasibility of taking into account the impact of sanctions restrictions on the competitiveness of the economy of our country, its industries and individual enterprises in relation to their implementation of plans and programs for their development within the framework of developed import substitution strategies.

Purpose of the study.

The main goal of the study is to clarify the economic essence of the concept of competitiveness, as well as to identify its components in relation to modern conditions for the development of the Russian economy.

Materials and methods.

To achieve this goal, the study used methods of synthesis and analysis of economic information.

Results and discussion.

The concept of "competitiveness" in modern economic theory characterizes various categories in relation to different economic entities and their activities in domestic and foreign markets, starting with individual enterprises and ending with individual sectors of the economy, as well as the country's economy as a whole. At the same time, under the influence of sanctions restrictions for the competitiveness of various economic categories and various economic entities, certain conditions for the perception of this category are formed. Based on theoretical premises, we will use a system of hierarchy of relations between different economic categories to which the concept of competitiveness is applied. It is presented in the form of a chain "country – industry – enterprise – product". To illustrate this hierarchy, some scientists use a concept such as the "pyramid of competitiveness" [2], the levels of which form interpretations of the concept of competitiveness in relation to the above chain of categories.

It is quite natural that for different categories in the definitions of the concept of competitiveness there are dependencies expressed in a certain way. Thus, the com-

petitiveness of a country's economy is determined by the competitiveness of its industries, which is formed under the influence of the competitiveness of specific enterprises, and it, in turn, depends on the ability of them to produce competitive products. However, the production of competitive products requires the creation of certain conditions both at the enterprise itself and on the scale of an individual industry, as well as the country's economy. Therefore, the concept of the category of competitiveness in relation to economic entities at any of the lower levels of the hierarchy becomes a competitiveness factor for economic entities at the upper levels of the hierarchy. At the same time, in the hierarchy of economic entities at the upper levels, conditions are also formed that can be considered factors for ensuring the competitiveness of economic entities at the lower levels [3].

Therefore, it is no coincidence that there are significant differences in the definitions of the concept of competitiveness for different economic entities. So, firstly, relative to the country and the enterprise, these concepts are characterized by different target functions. Secondly, in relation to the development of specific countries, the target functions have significant differences due to historically established economic structures. Thirdly, the economic potential of countries and individual enterprises also varies significantly. In addition, the competitiveness of a country's economy can be represented based on its external or internal competitiveness. The development of the external competitiveness of the country's economy depends on such indicators as the share of products of individual industries in exports, demand for manufactured products, export structure, stability of the balance of payments, etc. Naturally, the effect of sanctions restrictions will negatively affect these and a number of other indicators characterizing external competitiveness the country's economy. These circumstances may cause certain contradictions in the internal and external interests of the strategic development of both the economy of an individual enterprise and the economy of the country as a whole.

The concept of competitiveness can be conditionally detailed by levels. At the macroeconomic level, the operating conditions of the economies of individual countries are formed, which determine their competitiveness in the global economy. At the meso-level, prospects for the development of industries, clusters and other associations of enterprises are formed, the competitiveness of which is determined on the scale of the country's economy. At the micro level, the conditions for the competitiveness of an enterprise and its products are formed, which depend on a whole group of multidirectional factors [4].

The peculiarities of the concept of competitiveness include the possibility of its quantitative assessment, for example, using an indicator of the level of competitiveness. To obtain quantitative assessments of competitiveness, it is necessary to have a subject, object and purpose of assessment. The subject is usually gov-

ernment economic management structures, as well as other interested structures. The objects of assessment are most often enterprises, as well as the products and services they produce. The main goals of the assessment are to determine indicators that reflect the position of economic entities in the market, for example, such as the dynamics of production, solvency in long- and short-term periods, etc. [5]. Since sanctions restrictions have an impact on the above and a number of other indicators, taking them into account when obtaining quantitative estimates of the competitiveness of economic entities will reflect modern features of determining its economic essence.

An important feature of competitiveness is the dynamics of its changes over time, which depends on the duration of the life cycle of an economic entity, the influence of external and internal environmental factors on its activities, and other circumstances.

Important features of the concept of competitiveness of economic entities include the ability to manage it as a key parameter of their strategic development. In addition, the concept of competitiveness of economic entities has such a feature as inconsistency, which is caused by the need to respect the interests of product manufacturers and their potential consumers.

In order to minimize the negative impact of sanctions restrictions at the industry level, more than twenty import substitution strategies were developed, within the framework of which enterprises in leading industries had to ensure the implementation of individual plans and programs aimed at carrying out their comprehensive modernization, localizing the production of replaced equipment, components and technologies in our country, ensuring the quality of products at the level of world standards [6].

In the conditions of the negative impact of sanctions restrictions, the level of their competitiveness can be considered a criterion indicator for assessing the economic condition of enterprises, and the possibility of reasonable management of their competitiveness was used as a determining condition for the strategic development of domestic enterprises. The level of competitiveness has a decisive influence on the quality of products produced by enterprises, the possibility of them receiving additional income and profit, their adaptation to functioning under sanctions restrictions, and the prospects for their economic growth [7]. The level of competitiveness of an enterprise is a complex indicator, which is determined depending on such factors as the competitiveness of the products it produces, the share of the products produced by the enterprise in the total market volume, opportunities to enter new, including international, markets, the presence of competitors in the market, market homogeneity by types of products sold, prospects for introducing innovations, etc.

The concept of “competitiveness of an enterprise” cannot be considered as a constant value, since it undergoes certain changes over time and depending on the

specific conditions in which the enterprise operates. This concept is influenced by a large number of objective and subjective factors of the external and internal environment, which can also change over time. Taking into account the combination of these factors, in essence, the direct formation of an indicator of the enterprise's competitiveness occurs. Conventionally, all factors can be combined into three groups: economic, entrepreneurial and regulatory.

Economic factors include such as the quality of the products produced, the cost of their sales, costs associated with the operation of the product or its consumption. Obviously, these factors depend on labor productivity, the level of innovation in production methods, management and organization of enterprise activities.

Entrepreneurial factors determine the conditions for the sale of products produced by an enterprise in foreign and domestic markets. This group of factors includes indicators that characterize:

- level of competition, the ratio of supply and demand for products manufactured by the enterprise on the market, etc.;
- the level of service for products manufactured by the enterprise during its operation in terms of the availability of warranty and technical service points, the quality of the services they provide;
- the degree of influence of advertising of products manufactured by the enterprise on potential consumers;
- business reputation of the enterprise, the presence of an image or a well-known brand, trademark, etc.

Regulatory and legal factors combine mandatory requirements for all enterprises for the safe use of their products by consumers. If the enterprise's products do not comply with the requirements of current norms, standards and legislation, they are subject to rejection.

The concept of an enterprise's competitiveness extends to its potential capabilities, as well as dynamic adaptation to the negative impact of sanctions restrictions. The presence of material, technical, innovative and other potential at the enterprise will contribute to the production of established volumes of competitive products that allow satisfying consumer demands. The competitiveness potential of an enterprise can be represented as a complex of its reserves and capabilities, on the basis of which additional competitive advantages of the enterprise can be formed, ensuring that it achieves its strategic development goals. The following elements can be distinguished as part of the competitiveness potential of an enterprise:

- production capacity of the enterprise and real opportunities to increase its load;
- capital structure and the possibility of increasing its use to strengthen the financial position of the enterprise;

- business reputation of the enterprise, strengthening its image;
- opportunities to increase the production of high-quality innovative products to obtain additional competitive advantages for the enterprise;
- qualification of enterprise personnel and creation of conditions for managing professional growth, modern organization of production.

Under the conditions of the negative impact of sanctions restrictions, increasing the competitiveness of an enterprise will be determined, on the one hand, by a targeted impact on various elements of its potential, and on the other hand, by the search for new opportunities in terms of managing the production activities of the enterprise while maximizing the use of its existing potential.

The constituent elements of the concept of enterprise competitiveness are complex multifactorial characteristics that can be independent objects of management. An enterprise can ensure its competitiveness only by promptly responding to dynamic changes in environmental factors.

Currently, a difficult situation has developed in the global economy, which is characterized by the constant improvement of methods of international economic cooperation, the need to defend national interests, and the expansion of the practice of introducing sanctions restrictions under far-fetched pretexts and bypassing international cooperation organizations. In these conditions, to maintain and grow competitiveness, primarily in international markets, enterprises need to use new approaches to organizing production and management.

Conclusion

Based on the conducted research, the following conclusions can be formulated:

1. It has been established that sanctions restrictions should be considered as an additional factor in the negative impact of the external environment on the development of production of many Russian enterprises. Therefore, there is a need to take into account their impact on the competitiveness of individual enterprises and industries, as well as the economy of our country as a whole.

2. New features of the concept of competitiveness are identified, which were a consequence of the influence of sanctions restrictions. These include the possibility of obtaining quantitative and relative assessments of competitiveness, managing it as one of the key parameters of the strategic development of economic entities, the dynamics of its changes over time, the contradictory interests of producers of products and services and their potential consumers.

3. The constituent elements of the concept of enterprise competitiveness, which represent complex multifactorial characteristics and can be independent objects of management, are considered.

References

1. Tsikin A.M. *Features of ensuring the competitiveness of the national economy under the sanctions regime* // *Philosophy of Economics*, 2016. No. 3(105). pp. 116-118.
2. Benz D.S., Silova E.S. *Theory of competition: Pro et contra* // *Bulletin of ChelSU*. 2018. No. 3 (413). URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/teoriyakonkurentsii-pro-et-contra>(date of access: 04/01/2024).
3. Nikiforova E.V. *On issues of sustainable development of economic entities* // *Balkan Scientific Review*. Volume 3, No. 2 (4), 2019. pp. 106-111.
4. Bataeva, BS *Development of Conditions of Innovations Institutionalization Contributing to the Russian Sustainable Development* // *Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems*. 2021. Vol. 160 LNNS. pp. 48-53.
5. Zharov A.N., Makeev I.S. *Theoretical approaches to the concept and assessment of competitiveness* // *Peoples' Friendship University of Russia*. 2016. No. 10-3(75). pp. 1142-1144.
6. Tsikin A.M. *Formation of competitiveness in the conditions of new challenges and restrictions* // *Bulletin of TVGU. Series "Economics and Management"*, 2017. No. 2. pp. 44-49.
7. Tsuprun V.S. *The concept and influence of competition and competitiveness in a market economy* // *Young scientist*. 2020. No. 18(308). pp. 171-173. URL: <https://moluch.ru/archive/308/69527/> (access date: 04/01/2024).